

Totally false 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Totally true

this scale is used for all measures of stigma

SSS stereotypes

1. Pessimistic prognosis (Jorm et al, 1999) #PPSS

Most people with schizophrenia can recover (live satisfying, productive, and hopeful lives despite the illness).

Most people with schizophrenia will have many re-hospitalizations.

Most people with schizophrenia will attempt suicide.

2. Incompetence (Magliano et al, 2004, Valery et al, in press, Stuber et al, 2014) #ISS

Most people with schizophrenia are able to participate in decisions about their treatment.

Most people with schizophrenia need guardianship.

Most people with schizophrenia are not able to work.

3. Danger (Grusgruber et al 2006, VanDorn et al, 2005) #DSS

Most people with schizophrenia are not dangerous to others.

Most people with schizophrenia have difficulty controlling their aggression.

Most people with schizophrenia should not be entrusted with young children, as this could be dangerous for the children.

4. Blame#BSS

Most people with schizophrenia have nothing to do with the onset of their illness.

Most people with schizophrenia are responsible for the onset of their illness through their behaviours (isolation, addiction, etc...).

Most people with schizophrenia have behaviours in their lives (isolation, addiction, etc.) that keep them in the disease.

*Most people with schizophrenia work hard to get better.

5. Infrahumanization (Leyens 2006) #InfSS

See Alice for instructions?

In your opinion, most people with schizophrenia are able to feel a sense of :

Joy

Fear

Pleasure

Surprise

Disgust

Anger

Serenity

Compassion

Shame

Contempt

Love

Guilt

SPS Bias

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Not at all	Slightly	A little	Moderately	Rather	Many	Extremely

Most people with schizophrenia make me feel :

- empathy/compassion?
- anxiety
- of fear
- of contempt
- disgust
- of sadness
- of joy
- of serenity

SDS Discrimination

6. *Desire for social distance (Modgill, 2014: in Opening Minds Stigma Scale for Health CareProviders, translated and back-translated by 2 native speakers) #SDDS*

If a colleague I work with told me he or she had treated schizophrenia, I would still want to work with him or her.

I would like to know if there is a link between schizophrenia and Alzheimer's disease.

Measures of variables related to the stigma of professionals

7. Recovery-oriented practices #ROPS

Based on the 6 dimensions of recovery-oriented practice (Mental Health Commission of Canada, 2016) (Leamy, Bird et al, 2014)

Never 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Always

Rop1: I use hopeful and optimistic language with people who have schizophrenia.

Rop2: In my work, I explain the advantages and disadvantages of my actions and give people with schizophrenia the opportunity to refuse what I propose.

Rop3: When I accompany someone with schizophrenia, I inform them of their rights (or make sure my colleagues do).

Rop4: When I support someone with schizophrenia, I involve the family or carers as care/support partners (or make sure my colleagues do).

Aop5: In my practice, I am attentive to the integration of people with schizophrenia into the community

Rop6: In my practice, I recommend that people with schizophrenia get in touch with people who have recovered from schizophrenia, via associations or a peer-to-peer/peer-helper health mediator (or I make sure my colleagues do).

8. Etiological beliefs (Valery et al, in press) #ECS

strongly disagree 1234567 strongly agree

Do you believe that genetic/hereditary predispositions are the cause of schizophrenia

You believe that chemical and anatomical abnormalities in the brain are the cause of schizophrenia

According to you, one or more psychological trauma(s) are at the origin of schizophrenia

According to you, a socially solitary personality, preferring to be socially withdrawn, is at the origin of schizophrenia

In your opinion, various family problems (communication, abuse, neglect...) are at the origin of schizophrenia

In your opinion, performance pressures (academic or professional) are at the root of schizophrenia

9. Cognitive View of Schizophrenia (Valery et al, in press) CBS

According to you, cognitive deficits in schizophrenia are a source of psychic disability.

According to you, deficits in executive function, memory and social cognition are at play in schizophrenia.

According to you, cognitive dysfunctions are the cause of schizophrenia.

10. Continuum belief (Violeau et al, coming soon) #CC S

Schizophrenia is simply an exaggeration of normal functioning.

*Schizophrenia symptoms, such as hearing voices or feeling persecuted, are actually common in everyone

There is a clear and well-defined boundary between schizophrenia and normality.

Schizophrenia involves a fundamentally different state of mind from normal.

11. Sense of utility (Lebowitz et al, 2014) SUCS#

strongly disagree 1234567 strongly agree

What I do in my work is useful in the care of people with schizophrenia.

My work with people who have schizophrenia plays an important role in their recovery.

I feel effective in my work with people who have schizophrenia.

12. Moral correctness and ethical conflict

strongly disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 strongly agree

In my work with people who have schizophrenia, I do things that make me morally uncomfortable.

In my work with people with schizophrenia, I do things that go against my principles

13. Incremental vision (Violeau et al, coming soon)

Sub-scale view of schizophrenia as a disease that cannot evolve

In your opinion, the symptoms of schizophrenia are changing :

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Not at all			Moderately		Considerably	

Sub-scale of schizophrenia as an unmanageable disease

It is possible to act on the symptoms of schizophrenia:

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Not at all			Moderately		Considerably	

14. Similarities (Violeau et al, coming soon)

strongly disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 strongly agree

I share similarities with people who have schizophrenia.

I have a lot in common with people who have schizophrenia.

15. Mastery of knowledge

In your **initial training**, did you learn about :

Schizophrenia: Yes/No

Psychological disability: Yes/No

Psychosocial rehabilitation: Yes/No

The notion of Recovery: Yes/No

- Stigma: Yes/No

In your **continuing education**, have you had any lessons on :

Schizophrenia: Yes/No

Psychological disability: Yes/No

Psychosocial rehabilitation: Yes/No

The notion of Recovery: Yes/No

Stigma: Yes/No

If you had the opportunity, would you like additional training :

- Recovery-oriented practices
- Stigma

Socio-demographic issues

Variable	Question	Answer choices	Modality
Sex	You are :	One Woman/One Man/Other	
Age	Please indicate your age:	Open Question	Limited to numbers, limited to 2 characters
MHP in France	Do you practice your profession in France?	Yes/No	
School level	Last grade completed	Primary School College High School Bin BTS License Master Doctorate of Practice (Medicine, Pharmacy, Dentistry) Research Doctorate	Unique choice
Current professional ?	Do you currently work with people suffering from schizophrenia?	Currently yes Currently not, but I have worked with people suffering from schizophrenia - Never	Unique choice
Profession		Psychiatrist Nurse Caregiver Occupational Therapist Speech-Language Pathologist Psychologist Educator Monitor Social Services Assistants Animator Secretary Hospital Service Officer Other: ...	Unique choice
Neuropsychologist	Are you also a neuropsychologist	Yes/No	If answered "Psychologist" to the above. Unique choice
Theoretical repository you	You situate your practice as belonging primarily to the theoretical framework:	Psychoanalytical or psychodynamic - Cognitive-Behavioral - Systemic Neuropsychological Humanist Biological - DK	Unique choice

Theoretical service benchmark	What is the main theoretical orientation in your department?		
Structure	Currently, in which type of service/structure do you mainly work?	<p>Full-time hospitalization service</p> <p>Day hospital</p> <p>Psychosocial Rehabilitation Service</p> <p>Medical and Psychological Centre</p> <p>SAMSAH</p> <p>SAVS</p> <p>Association</p> <p>Professional retraining centre</p> <p>ESAT</p> <p>Residential homes (FAM, MDR, etc...)</p> <p>SRH</p> <p>- Liberal activity</p> <p>Other...</p>	Single Choice
Multidisciplinarity	Do you work in a multidisciplinary team	Yes/No	
Multidisciplinarity	The team in which you work is composed of :	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Neuropsychologist - Occupational Therapist - Health Mediator/Pair - Pair-Aidant - None of these three 	
Region	In which department do you practice? Indicate the number	Open Question	Limited to numbers, limited to 2 characters
Years of experience	How many years of experience do you have in your profession?	Open Question	Limited to numbers, limited to 2 characters
Familiarity with schizophrenia	"Do you have someone in your life who suffers from a schizophrenic spectrum disorder?"	<p>No</p> <p>Yes, among my colleagues</p> <p>Yes, in my neighbourhood</p> <p>Yes, in my circle of friends</p> <p>- Yes, in my circle: close family (parent, child, spouse, brother, sister)</p> <p>Yes, in my circle: extended family</p>	Multiple Choice

		Yes, I do.	

Finally, do you have any ideas/solutions to share with us that promote less stigmatizing practices towards people with schizophrenia?

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If you had the opportunity, would you accept an audit of your professional practice? Yes/No question
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